

Table 1. Overview of CVD-generated hollow and core-shell carbon nanostructures.

Catalyst or Template Type	Carbon Source (Feedstock)	Temperature (°C)	Morphology / Product	Mechanistic Highlights	Ref.
Ni/Al ₂ O ₃ (reduced NiO)	CH ₄ + H ₂	600	Hollow CNOs (~50 nm)	Carbon dissolution-precipitation; Kirkendall voiding	[63]
Co on MgO (1-10 wt%)	C ₂ H ₄ + Ar	700	Hollow onions (10-50 nm, 99% purity)	Co decomposes C ₂ H ₄ ; MgO prevents sintering	[62]
MgO, Al ₂ O ₃ , TiO ₂	C ₂ H ₅ OH	700-800	Few-layer graphene shells (3-7 layers)	Oxide templating; surface oxygen enables functionalization	[64]
MgO nanospheres	CH ₄ + H ₂	800	Hollow graphitic spheres	MgO-templated graphitization; durable electrodes	[66]
SiO ₂ or Au@SiO ₂	CH ₄	700-900	Hollow or core-shell spheres	Geometric templating via SiO ₂ ; HF removal	[67]
SiO ₂ /AAO templates	Polyphenol vapor	500-950 (ramp)	Hollow carbons (porous)	Non-isothermal CVD; shell thickness control	[68]
SiO ₂ nanoparticles	CH ₄	1000	SiC/graphene core-shell	Partial SiO ₂ → SiC; oxide-carbide transition	[69]
Si nanoparticles + vertical graphene	CVD carbon + H ₂	700-800	core-shell Si-C	Vertically aligned graphene improves conductivity	[70]
SiO ₂ template + CVD carbon	C ₂ H ₂	750	core-shell Si-C composite	Controlled voids buffer Si expansion	[71]
Metal-free (self-template)	CVD carbon precursor	700	Al-doped hollow cages	Atomic Al doping tunes Li ⁺ intercalation	[72]
Dolomite template	CVD + Triphenylphosphine	700	P-doped hollow spheres	P creates electron-rich redox sites	[73]
Dolomite + N-source	CVD + NH ₃	750	N-doped hollow carbons	Multiscale porosity; improved ion transport	[74]